

Termination patterns of *Karenia brevis* blooms in the eastern Gulf of Mexico

Cynthia A. Heil^{1*}, Shady A. Amin², Patricia M. Glibert³, Katherine A. Hubbard⁴, Ming Li³, Joaquín Martínez Martínez⁵, Robert Weisberg⁶, Yonggang Liu⁶, Yunfang Sun⁶

¹ Mote Marine Laboratory, 1600 Ken Thompson Pky, Sarasota, Florida 34236, U.S.A.; ² New York University – Abu Dhabi, Experimental Research Building (C1) RL5-20, Abu Dhabi, U.A.E.;

³ University of Maryland Center for Environmental Science, Horn Point Laboratory, PO Box 775, Cambridge, MD 21613, U.S.A.; ⁴ Florida Fish and Wildlife Conservation Commission, Fish and Wildlife Research Institute, 100 8th St S.E., St. Petersburg, Florida, 33701, U.S.A.; ⁵ Bigelow Laboratory for Ocean Sciences, 60 Bigelow Dr., East Boothbay, Maine, 04544, U.S.A.; ⁶ College of Marine Science, University of South Florida, 140 7th Ave. S., St. Petersburg, Florida, 33701, U.S.A.

* corresponding author's email: cheil@mote.org

Abstract

The factors governing the initiation and development of *K. brevis* blooms in the eastern Gulf of Mexico are fairly well understood, however the physical, chemical and biological factors underlying bloom transport and termination are not. The Florida Fish and Wildlife Conservation Commission's HAB Monitoring database was analyzed from 1998 - 2021 for temporal trends in bloom duration, initiation and termination and for repetitive spatial patterns in bloom termination. A unimodal pattern in bloom initiation was observed, with the most frequent initiations in September. Bloom termination was more variable, with the most frequent occurrences in April. Four recurring patterns in bloom termination were identified during this period for southwest Florida *K. brevis* blooms: 1) coastal transport south to the Florida Keys then west into the Gulf of Mexico, 2) transport to the Florida Panhandle with subsequent termination in place, or 3) via coastal transport west to Alabama, and 4) termination in place in southwest Florida. These patterns suggest that consistent physical, chemical and biological drivers underlie the termination stages of *K. brevis* blooms, and that identification of these drivers may provide useful management tools for bloom prediction and monitoring.

Keywords: *Karenia brevis*, Florida Red tide, initiation, termination, Florida HAB Historical Database

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Introduction

Blooms of the toxic dinoflagellate *Karenia brevis* are an annual feature of the eastern Gulf of Mexico (GoM), resulting in significant environmental, human health and economic impacts (Heil and Muni-Morgan, 2021). Much is known about physical, chemical and biological factors that underlie these blooms' initiation and development stages. Physical drivers and a complex nutrient pathway sometimes involving cyanobacteria (Steidinger, 1975; Lenes *et al.*, 2001; Walsh and Steidinger, 2001) have been shown to be crucial to offshore initiation stages. Offshore upwelling related to Loop Current intrusion plays a complex role in initiation. Some upwelling is required for initiation (Liu *et al.*, 2012; Weisberg *et al.*, 2014), however too much can deliver upwelled NO_3^- to the shelf, potentially favoring other taxa and impeding *Karenia* growth (Heil *et al.*, 2001; Weisberg *et al.*, 2016). Cross-shelf cell transport subsequently occurs via the bottom Ekman layer (Weisberg *et al.*, 2009, 2016), driven by wind-driven and upwelling-related transport. The slow-growing *K. brevis* cells are eventually transported and concentrated toward the shore by winds, frontal systems and longshore currents (Vargo *et al.*, 2001; Weisberg and He, 2003), where these cells may thrive and persist in bloom concentrations for periods of months to years (Steidinger, 2009) and where a variety of nutrient sources of nutrients may support their growth (Heil *et al.*, 2014).

Little is known of the factors influencing bloom termination, however. Physical factors resulting in flow divergence, disrupting bloom integrity (Slobodkin, 1953) or physical transport and dilution of blooms to offshore or

other regions (Steidinger, 2009) are thought to contribute to termination. However nutrient deprivation (Steidinger, 2009; Vargo, 2009) and bacterial and viral interactions (Mayali and Doucette, 2002; Roth *et al.*, 2007; Lenes *et al.*, 2013; Meyer *et al.*, 2014) may also potentially influence termination. As an initial step in the examination of physical, nutrient and biological factors underlying *K. brevis* bloom termination in the eastern GoM, *K. brevis* bloom records from 1998 to 2021 from the Florida Fish and Wildlife Conservation Commission's (FWC) HAB Monitoring Database were examined for repetitive patterns in both spatial and temporal bloom termination.

Material and Methods

Karenia brevis data were obtained from the FWC Database (<https://myfwc.com/research/redtide/monitoring/database/>). This database contains data collected from diverse sources and includes samples collected during research, routine monitoring, and event response sampling of suspected or confirmed *K. brevis* events. This analysis is limited to data post-1998 when routine sampling intensified, but the database contains records dating back to 1953.

Data included geo-referenced *K. brevis* concentrations with the associated date, time, depth, and collecting agencies for all sites within Florida estuarine, coastal and offshore locations during the time period. This time span was chosen for analysis as it includes the start of a regional study for which repetitive monthly shelf sampling was conducted, so ancillary data are available for

future examination of physical, nutrient and biological conditions underlying observed patterns. The month of bloom initiation was defined as a sustained (>1 month) period of *K. brevis* concentrations greater than 2.0×10^3 cells L^{-1} after more than 2 months of background ($<1.0 \times 10^3$ cells L^{-1}) cell concentrations. Bloom termination was defined as a period of > 6 weeks of *K. brevis* cell concentrations at or below background concentrations. Analysis of bloom termination trends from 2000 to 2021 was conducted using FWC's archived status maps (<https://www.flickr.com/photos/myfwc/sets/72157635398013168/>), supplemented with the database for the years 1998 and 1999.

Results and Discussion

No pattern was evident in bloom duration (Fig. 1); blooms lasted from three to 17 months. However, Sobrinho *et al.* (this volume), using the same database, found that freshwater discharge and climate variations as measured by El Niño – Southern Oscillation (ENSO) had direct and indirect roles in timing and magnitude of blooms. The longest bloom durations were observed in the 2004-2005 and 2017-2019 blooms, which extended through the summers into the following years and were associated with significant environmental impacts and economic losses.

Fig. 1. Duration of *K. brevis* blooms in the GoM as measured from the year the bloom initiated.

Over the 22 years examined, bloom initiation month displayed a unimodal trend, with six blooms initiating in September, four each in August and October and two in July and November (Fig. 2). Bloom termination was observed in all months, from December through June (except January). The maximum number of bloom terminations (six) was observed in April, suggesting that as yet unidentified conditions in April may serve as a 'gate' to potential bloom extension into the summer months. It is of note that in typical years, Florida experiences a shift from the winter dry season to the summer rainy season by mid-May. Delays in the timing of the wet season and related nutrient inputs may be one potential factor influencing bloom duration.

Fig. 2. Monthly distribution of *K. brevis* bloom initiation and termination events from 1998- 2021.

The most common pattern of termination for southwest Florida coastal *K. brevis* blooms (70%) was coastal transport of the bloom south toward the Florida Keys region then west into the GoM (the ‘Everglades Off Ramp’ pattern) as was demonstrated in 2007 and 2008 blooms (Table 1, Fig. 3a). A small percentage of these southwest transported blooms (19%) were transported through the Keys and up the eastern Florida coast (e.g. 2007, 2012 and 2018 blooms; Fig. 3b). However, when this occurred it did not result in termination of the original bloom in the southwest region. The fate of bloom populations transported west into the GoM is unknown.

A smaller percentage (57%) of southwest Florida blooms was displaced to the Panhandle region, where they either terminated in place within two months (e.g., 2013 bloom; Fig. 3c) or were transported west to Alabama (e.g., 2005 and 2018 blooms; Fig. 3d). Blooms in the Panhandle region were preceded by southwest Florida blooms 83% of the time and both termination patterns could occur simultaneously for spatially separated subpopulations of the same Panhandle regional population.

Fig. 3. Examples of the termination patterns described in text. Panels in column a (2008) represent the Everglades off-ramp; panels in column b (2018) represent blooms that were transported through the Keys and up the east coast. Arrows indicate most intense bloom area.

Table 1. Patterns of *K. brevis* bloom termination in the eastern GoM from 1998-2021 expressed as a percentage of southwest Florida blooms.

Pattern	Description	Occurrence
1. Everglades Off Ramp	Southeast coastal transport to Keys, then west into Gulf	70%
2. Panhandle Termination	Transport to Panhandle from SW FL	57%
A. Termination in place	Bloom ends within 1-2 months in place	92%
B. Transport	Bloom transported west to AL from area of 1st appearance	38%
3. Southwest FL Termination	Bloom concentrations reduced in place	20%

In some years, blooms were observed to terminate in place in southwest Florida without coastal transport. As this usually occurred during the late dry season (e.g., May 2013), it is possible that nutrient depletion played a greater role in termination of these blooms.

Offshore expansion of established coastal blooms in the Naples to Cedar Key region was observed during the August-September period of the 2005 bloom and the September through October period of the 2018 bloom (Figs. 3b,d). Both expansion periods were associated with unusual, environmentally destructive (e.g., associated regional anoxia and extensive marine wildlife mortalities) over-summering blooms and neither expansion resulted in bloom termination.

Fig. 3, cont'd. Panels in line c (2013) represent blooms that terminated in place; and panels in line d (2005) represent blooms with offshore expansion. Green dots represent no bloom; yellow, orange, and red dots represent increasing *K. brevis* cell concentrations. Arrows indicate most intense bloom areas.

The patterns identified here suggest that consistent, identifiable physical, nutrient and biological drivers underlie bloom termination stages, and that identification of these drivers may provide useful management tools for bloom prediction and monitoring.

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